

Convolutional Neural Networks and Long Short Term Memory for Phishing Email Classification

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Abstract— The focus on this work is on classifying phishing emails using deep neural networks. Since phishing emails have no specific characteristic, they are difficult to detect and classify, and little research has been done on the detection of phishing emails. In this work, two deep neural networks, Long Short Term Memory (LSTM), a form of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), were compared and used for classification of phishing emails. RNN is the most used neural network for text classification. CNNs have also shown to be effective in text classification. In addition to tuning hyperparameters, different activation functions and optimizers are used for comparing the performance of CNN and LSTM on the basis of accuracy and the ROC-score. LSTM achieved a higher accuracy than CNN, and overall the Adam Optimizer performed better than the SGD optimizer. The best parameters for higher accuracy and ROC-score are also presented.

Keywords: *Phishing Email Classification; Convolutional Neural Networks; Long Short Term Memory; Hyperparameters; Recurrent Neural Networks; Deep Learning*

I. INTRODUCTION

Phishing is a cleverly crafted social engineering attack that is characterized by an attacker imitating a trustworthy source to gain confidential and private information from a user for malicious purposes [1, 2]. Phishing attacks, primarily carried out via email [3] or other electronic communication channels [4], affect both businesses and private individuals [2], and since emails are widely used in both personal and professional contexts, phishing has become a rising threat [5]. In 2019 alone, more than 114,000 private individuals in the US lost in total more than \$57.8 million through phishing [6]. In the same year, 90% of all organizations experienced targeted phishing attacks [7].

Phishing attackers also exploit any crisis, and the coronavirus outbreak has been no different [8]. Google's Threat Analysis Group reported that they blocked 18 million COVID-19 phishing emails per day in mid-April of 2020 [8]. Amidst the spike in remote work tied to the COVID-19 pandemic, phishing campaigns have even been targeting remote working software like Skype and Zoom [9]. Attackers sent phishing emails looking eerily similar to legitimate pending notifications coming from Skype or Zoom, with a sender's address that appears very legitimate at first and a very convincing landing page [9].

The focus on this work is on classifying phishing emails. Since phishing emails have no specific characteristic, they are difficult to detect and classify, and little research has been done on the detection of phishing emails. In this work, two different deep neural networks, Long Short Term Memory (LSTM), a form of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), were compared and used for classification of phishing emails. RNN is the most used neural network for text classification. CNNs have also shown to be effective in text classification. In this work, in addition to tuning hyperparameters, different activation functions and optimizers are used for comparing the performance of CNN and LSTM on the basis of accuracy and the ROC-score.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the related works. Section 3 presents the data and preprocessing technique used. Section 4 presents the algorithms, CNN, RNN and LSTM. Section 5 presents the experimental design and parameters and section 6 presents the results and discussion. The last section, Section 7, is the conclusion.

II. RELATED WORKS

Several papers have shown that the CNN shows good performance for text classification. [10] applied CNN for sentence classification and achieved good results by using hyperparameter tuning. [10] included a dropout on the last layer and found the best hyperparameters by applying a grid search on one of the development data sets. In this work, six data sets were used to train and evaluate the performance of CNN for text classification. Several variations of the CNN were implemented and compared. The result was that even the simple CNN-model performed pretty well, but improvements can be made by fine-tuning (e.g. multi-channel for static CNN).

[11] performed an empirical exploration on the user of character-level CNN (ConvNets) for text classification, and showed how CNN can achieve competitive results. In this work, One-Hot Encoding was applied on characters and compared to traditional models such as bag of words, n -grams and their TFIDIF variants. This work compared CNN with LSTM.

Another work that made use of the One-Hot Encoding for text classification was [12]. This work analyzed the use of

discrete-time RNN and its capability for predicting the next symbol in a sequence in order to implement a model. This study, however, focused more on online prediction.

[13] used RNN to classify textual data. In this work, on the basis of RNNs, three different architectures are implemented and compared. All showed good performance in classification of textual data.

[14] focused on extracting and analyzing features of emails, and using the most important features for a multi-classifier prediction model. J48, SVM and IB1 were used in the multi-classifier prediction model. The dataset used in this study was a publicly accessible dataset. These results showed that a single classifier would not be enough to classify phishing emails, and they were able to achieve almost perfect accuracy with their multi-classifier model (a low false positive rate).

[15] also covered the classification of phishing. Features that were used in this work were, age of the domain name, IP address, number of domains or key words.

III. THE DATA AND PREPROCESSING

A. The Data

The dataset was provided by AppRiver, a company headquartered in Pensacola, Florida, USA, that offers secure cloud-based cybersecurity solutions. The dataset contains 18,365 emails, of which 3,416 are phishing emails.

B. Preprocessing: One-Hot Encoding

Phishing data, rather, phishing email data, is mostly text data. One-Hot Encoding was applied to transform this textual data into numerical vectors. One-Hot Encoding works as follows: It takes a word and assigns a vector containing only zeros and ones to that word. This vector then represents the specific word. To avoid the assignment of different outcomes of the same word to different vectors, tokenizing and lemmatizing methods are applied. Tokenizing refers to splitting the text into tokens, in our case words, where each token will be preprocessed separately. Lemmatizing is the transformation of words back to their stem using morphological techniques [16].

After lemmatizing, the vocabulary size needs to be set for the one-hot encoding. The vocabulary size describes how many different words should be assumed in the data. There are different approximations possible based on the size of the data. In this work the vocabulary size was set to 100. After setting the vocabulary size, each word will be one-hot encoded until all unit vectors are assigned to words. The remaining words will be assigned to a PAD vector, a vector only containing zeros.

Also, the maximum document length and the vocabulary size needs to be specified. The vocabulary size was set to 100 and the maximum document length to 70.

IV. ALGORITHMS

A. Convolutional Neural Networks

Studies have shown that CNN has performed well with text classification [10, 11]. CNN consists of several layers of convolutions. Activation functions are applied to the results of the layers of convolutions. CNN tries to find features that best characterize the data by using filters throughout the convolutional layers. Each layer applies different filters. The filter and its values are learned by the network during the training phase. For each filter (each text) the output of the convolutional layer is a vector. This vector contains values that are the sum of the component wise multiplication when applying the filter on each region of the matrix containing the text [17].

In the pooling layer, the results of the convolutional layer will be pooled. There are different ways of pooling, e.g. max-pooling or average-pooling. Max-pooling takes the maximum value of each vector while average-pooling calculates the average of each vector. The last layer of CNN is the fully connected layer. This layer combines the results from the prior layers, i.e. the extracted features with the classification of the data. It finds the features that best characterize the data in order to classify the data correctly [17].

B. Recurrent Neural Networks

Studies have also shown that RNN has been successful in text classification [11, 13]. RNNs are a neural network in which each neuron receives input from a prior neuron, produces an output for the next neuron and sends an output back to itself. This means the input a neuron gets at the time step t is the input corresponding to this time step and its output from the previous time step. Each input is weighted. Taking into account not only the previous time step, but all the time steps before the output of a neuron, is a function of all the inputs from the previous time steps. There are different ways of implementing RNN. The RNN of interest for phishing email classification feeds the network with a sequence of inputs and ignores all outputs except for the last one, i.e. sequence-to-vector network. This work focuses on the recurrent neural network, Long Short Term Memory (LSTM).

1) Long Short Term Memory

LSTM has been successfully used in text classification by [11]. The LSTM cell can be considered a black box, like a basic cell but with better performance. The training converges faster and it detects long-term dependencies in the data. The state of the LSTM is split in two vectors: $h(t)$ and $c(t)$ where $h(t)$ describes the short-term state and $c(t)$ the long-term state. The long-term state $c(t-1)$ goes through the network, passes a forget gate (where some memories can be dropped) and the addition operation to add new memory. The current input vector $x(t)$ and the previous short-term state $h(t-1)$ are fed to four different fully connected layers: The main layer is the one that outputs $g(t)$. The other layers are gate controllers: the forget gate, the input gate and the output gate. This means that, in general, an LSTM cell can learn to recognize an important input, store it in the long-term state, learn to keep it and learn to extract it whenever it is needed [18].

C. Activation Functions

In order to process the data through the different layers, activation functions are used. These functions are used to transform the activation level of a unit into an output signal. This specifies how much information of a unit should be transported to the next layer. In this work, the Sigmoid and ReLU activation functions were used. Figure 1 illustrates the Sigmoid and ReLU activation functions respectively.

Figure 1. Sigmoid and ReLU Activation Functions [25]

1) The Sigmoid Activation Function

The sigmoid activation function assigns a positive number between 0 and 1 to every input. The sigmoid activation function, one of the most used is most activation functions [19], is useful for training data that is between 0 and 1.

2) The Rectified Linear Unit

ReLU, the rectified linear unit, is conventionally applied as an activation function for hidden layers in a deep neural network but it can also be used to learn the weight parameters of the ReLU classification layer through backpropagation. It is defined as a maximum of zero and a specific input. This means that it always assigns a value greater or equal to zero [20].

V. EXPERIMENTATION

This section describes the parameters used for CNN and LSTM experimentations respectively.

A. Convolutional Neural Networks

First, the parameters that are used for CNN are described, and the next section describes how these parameters have been used.

1) Parameters Used for Convolutional Neural Networks

The experimental parameters that were used for CNN were: Number of channels, pooling method, dropout, Kernel size and the optimizer. Next the experimental parameters are explained.

Number of channels. The number of channels was kept at three.

Pooling method. Max-pooling takes the maximum value of each resulting vector of the convolutional layer while Average-pooling uses the average value of all entries of that vector [21]. Both Max-pooling and Average-pooling were used in this work.

Dropout. Dropouts are included in neural networks in order to avoid overfitting by dropping units when they exceed a specific value. Dropping a unit means excluding this unit and all connections of that unit in the neural network. A common value for the dropout rate is 0.5 [22]. The dropout rate was set to 0.5 in this work.

Kernel size. The kernel size is the size of the filters in the convolutional layer. Since it is necessary to use the same number of columns for the filter as the one-hot encoded matrix, a variation can be included in the number of rows of the filter. Commonly used numbers of rows, i.e. kernel sizes, are used in this work. The kernel size or the length of the 1d convolution window was set to 4, 6 and 8 (three different sizes for the three channels respectively).

Optimizer. Optimizer methods try to reduce the error of the model which can be measured by a loss function. Optimizing minimizes the loss function. The first optimizing method used was the stochastic gradient descent (SGD). This is a vector of partial derivatives. From this, the settings for minimal error can be calculated and the weights adjusted by using backpropagation [23]. The Adam Optimizer is generally better for working with high-dimensional parameter spaces. It combines the advantages of the AdaGrad (good performance with sparse gradients) and RMSProp (good performance for non-stationary settings) [26]. The Adam Optimizer and the Stochastic Gradient Descent were used in this work.

2) Experimental Design for CNN

Figure 2 presents the architecture for the design of experiments for CNN. For the filter sizes of 16, 32, 48 and 64, the following eight different settings were used. For Setting 1, the Sigmoid Activation Function, Max-pooling and Adam Optimizer were used. For setting 2, the Sigmoid Activation Function, Max-pooling and SGD optimizer were used, and so on.

Figure 2. Experimental Design for CNN

B. Experimental Parameters for Long Short Term Memory

The experimental parameters that were used for LSTM were, the optimizer, the maximum email length, the batch size and the number of epochs.

Optimizer. The Adam Optimizer and the Stochastic Gradient Descent were used.

Maximum Email Length. This was set to 500.

Batch size. Since the whole dataset should not be processed through the network at once, the dataset was split into batches, i.e. into smaller datasets. These were then fed to the neural network. The batch size was set to the commonly used batch size of 64.

The number of epochs. One epoch is when the whole dataset is passed forward and backward through the neural network only one time. Since optimizing a neural network is an iterative process, it is more efficient to not pass the whole dataset through the network at once. Low number for epochs can lead to underfitting (e.g. if the number of epochs is set to one), while a high number of epochs can lead to overfitting. Therefore, a balance has to be achieved to find the optimal balance between over- and underfitting [24]. In this work, the number of epochs was varied from 1 to 3.

1) Experimental Design for LSTM

Figure 3 presents the architecture for the design of experiments for LSTM. For Setting 1, the maximum email length was set to 500, batch size to 64, using one epoch, the Adam Optimizer, and the Sigmoid Activation Function. For setting 2, the maximum email length was set to 500, batch size

to 64, using one epoch, the Adam Optimizer, and the ReLU Activation Function, and so on.

Figure 3. Experimental Design for LSTM

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, first the measures of performance are presented, then the CNN and LSTM results are presented.

A. Measures of Performance

For a measure of performance, the accuracy, true/false positive rates and ROC-Score were used to measure the performance of the neural networks.

1) Accuracy

Accuracy is the ratio of correctly classified data.

2) True / False Positives

The false positive rate (FPR) is the ratio of non-phishing emails that were incorrectly classified as phishing emails. It can also be calculated by subtracting the ratio of correctly classified non-phishing emails from one. The true positive rate is the ratio of phishing emails that were correctly classified as phishing emails. The better a model, the higher the true positive rate, and the lower the false positive rate. The ROC curve plots TPR against FPR.

True and False Positive rates give a better impression of the fit of a model than accuracy, especially for data where the ratio of the classes is not equal. In this study, less than 20% of the total dataset were phishing emails. Hence, using only accuracy as a measure of the model fit can give an unusually high accuracy, which might not be correct.

3) The ROC-Curve

The ROC-curve shows the tradeoff between the true positive rates and the false positive rates (any increase in the true positive rates will be accompanied by a decrease in the false positive rates). The closer the curve follows the left border and the top border of the ROC space, the more accurate the test.

B. CNN Results

Figure 4 graphs each of the settings from Figure 2 by the number of filters and accuracy. Figure 4 shows that the number of filters did not have much of an effect on the accuracy of CNN. The settings, however, have an effect on the accuracy of CNN, hence this was further analyzed in Figures 5-8.

Figure 6. CNN Accuracy by Activation Function for 32 Filters

Figure 4. CNN Accuracy by Setting by Number of Filters

Figures 5-8 graph CNN accuracy by activation function for 16, 32, 48 and 64 filters respectively. In each of these figures, the first four bars of represent the usage of the sigmoid activation function and the second four bars represent the usage of the ReLU activation function.

Figure 7. CNN Accuracy by Activation Function for 48 Filters

Figure 5. CNN Accuracy by Activation Function for 16 Filters

Figure 1. CNN Accuracy by Activation Function for 64 Filters

Figures 5 – 8 show that:

- Overall, the ReLU Activation function performed better than the Sigmoid Activation function.
- The Adam Optimizer performed better than the SGD Optimizer, both for Average-pooling as well as Max-pooling, for both the Sigmoid as well as the ReLU activation functions.

Detailed results for the various runs, as per settings presented in Figure 2, are presented in Tables 1-8. Table 1 presents the results of the runs for Setting 1, Table 2 are the results of the runs for Setting 2, and so forth.

Number of Filters	Accuracy	ROC-Score
16	92.82 %	95.15 %
32	93.15 %	95.67 %
48	93.84 %	94.11 %
64	93.07 %	93.92 %

Table 1. Setting 1: Kernel size 4,6,8, Sigmoid activation function, 3 channels, Max-pooling, Adam optimizer

Number of Filters	Accuracy	ROC-Score
16	81.36 %	50.00 %
32	81.30 %	50.00 %
48	81.23 %	50.00 %
64	81.31 %	50.00 %

Table 2. Setting 2: Kernel size 4,6,8, Sigmoid activation function, 3 channels, Max-pooling, SGD optimizer

Number of Filters	Accuracy	ROC-Score
16	93.48 %	95.55 %
32	93.30 %	95.08 %
48	81.01 %	50.00 %
64	91.25 %	94.89 %

Table 3. Setting 3: Kernel size 4,6,8, Sigmoid activation function, 3 channels, Average-pooling, Adam optimizer

Number of Filters	Accuracy	ROC-Score
16	81.28 %	50.00 %
32	81.35 %	50.00 %
48	81.28 %	50.00 %
64	81.29 %	50.00 %

Table 4. Setting 4: Kernel size 4,6,8, Sigmoid activation function, 3 channels, Average-pooling, SGD optimizer

Number of Filters	Accuracy	ROC-Score
16	96.25 %	94.10%
32	96.10 %	96.28%
48	96.52%	96.16%
64	96.36%	96.16%

Table 5. Setting 5: Kernel size 4,6,8, ReLU activation function, 3 channels, Max-pooling, Adam optimizer

Number of Filters	Accuracy	ROC-Score
16	81.25 %	50.00 %
32	81.36 %	50.00 %
48	81.29 %	50.00 %
64	81.34 %	51.59 %

Table 6. Setting 6: Kernel size 4,6,8, ReLU activation function, 3 channels, Max-pooling, SGD optimizer

Number of Filters	Accuracy	ROC-Score
16	96.04 %	96.05 %
32	95.27 %	94.95 %
48	95.57 %	96.15 %
64	95.86 %	95.91 %

Table 7. Setting 7: Kernel size 4,6,8, ReLU activation function, 3 channels, Average-pooling, Adam optimizer

Number of Filters	Accuracy	ROC-Score
16	81.20 %	50.00 %
32	81.35 %	50.00 %
48	81.24 %	50.00 %
64	81.32 %	50.00 %

Table 8. Setting 8: Kernel size 4,6,8, ReLU activation function, 3 channels, Average-pooling, SGD optimizer

From Tables 1-8, it can be observed that:

- The highest accuracy (96.52%) as well as highest ROC-Score (96.16%) was obtained with Setting 5: Kernel size 4, 6, 8, ReLU activation function, 3 channels, Max-pooling, Adam optimizer, with 48 filters. The other filter sizes for this Setting, Setting 5, also had higher accuracy and ROC-scores than any other settings.
- The second highest accuracy as well as second highest ROC-score group can be considered as Setting 7: Kernel size 4, 6, 8, ReLU activation function, 3 channels, Average-pooling, Adam optimizer, with 16

filters, though the performance of the other filters (for this setting) were close.

- The Adam optimizer performed better than the SGD optimizer.
- Both the Sigmoid and ReLU Activation functions performed better with the Adam Optimizer.
- Both Max-pooling as well as Average-Pooling performed better with the Adam Optimizer.
- For CNN accuracy, it is difficult to say if the Sigmoid Activation performed better or the ReLU Activation function performed better. For the Sigmoid Activation function, Settings 1 and 3 gave good results, and for the ReLU Activation function, Settings 5 and 7 gave good results. Hence, other factors have to be considered besides the Activation function.

1) ROC-Curves

Figures 9 and 10 show the ROC-Curves for the ReLU and Sigmoid Activation functions respectively, for the best performing settings. The closer the curve follows the left border and the top border of the ROC space, the more accurate the test. For both of the graphs, Figures 9 and 10, we can observe that both activation functions had high results in terms of correctly classified data.

Figure 9. ROC Curve for CNN using the ReLU Activation function (the best performing settings)

Figure 10. ROC Curve for CNN using the Sigmoid Activation function (the best performing settings)

C. Long Short Term Memory Results

Figure 11 presents the LSTM accuracy by Activation function by each setting as per Figure 3 (the color codings are matched up to the color coding used in Figure 3 for the different settings, hence the legends are omitted in the following Figures).

Figure 11. LSTM Accuracy by Activation Function by Settings

Comparing the performance of LSTM for the two activation functions, Sigmoid and ReLU, from Figure 11 it can be observed that the sigmoid activation function performed better than the ReLU activation function for the LSTM model. In some cases, for the ReLU activation function, the LSTM model even had an accuracy of 0%.

Figure 12. LSTM Accuracy by Optimizer by Settings

Figure 12 compares the performance of LSTM for the two optimization methods used, for the different settings. As per Figure 12, the Adam optimizer performed better than the SGD Optimizer. The SGD optimizer had 0% accuracy for some runs.

The accuracy and ROC-score for the various runs as per the settings in Figure 3 are presented in Tables 9 – 14. The highest accuracy was obtained by the Setting 9: the Adam optimizer, max email length= 500, batch size= 64, 3 epochs, with the Sigmoid Activation function. This was an accuracy of 98.32% and the ROC-Score was 96.57%. The second highest accuracy was obtained using Setting 5: Adam optimizer, max email length= 500, batch size= 64, 2 epochs, with the Sigmoid Activation function. The second highest accuracy was 98.02% and the ROC-Score was 95.71%. And, the third highest accuracy was obtained using Setting 1: Adam optimizer, max email length= 500, batch size= 64, 1 epoch, with the Sigmoid Activation Function. The third highest accuracy was 97.85% and ROC-Score was 95.83%. All three highest accuracy scores obtained by LSTM were higher than the CNN accuracy scores.

Activation Function	Accuracy	ROC-Score
Sigmoid	97.85 %	95.38 %
ReLU	81.88 %	94.95 %

Table 9. Setting 1 & 2: Adam optimizer, max email length= 500, batch size= 64, 1 epoch

Activation Function	Accuracy	ROC-Score
Sigmoid	81.28 %	50.00 %
ReLU	0.00 %	50.00 %

Table 9. Setting 3 & 4: SGD optimizer, max email length= 500, batch size= 64, 1 epoch

Activation Function	Accuracy	ROC-Score
Sigmoid	98.02 %	95.71 %
ReLU	83.56 %	95.18 %

Table 10. Setting 5 & 6: Adam optimizer, max email length= 500, batch size= 64, 2 epochs

Activation Function	Accuracy	ROC-Score
Sigmoid	81.28 %	50.00 %
ReLU	81.28 %	50.00 %

Table 11. Setting 7 & 8: SGD optimizer, max email length= 500, batch size= 64, 2 epochs

Activation Function	Accuracy	ROC-Score
Sigmoid	98.32 %	96.57 %
ReLU	79.79 %	57.28 %

Table 12. Setting 9 & 10: Adam optimizer, max email length= 500, batch size= 64, 3 epochs

Activation Function	Accuracy	ROC-Score
Sigmoid	81.28 %	50.00 %
ReLU	0.00 %	50.00 %

Table 13. – Setting 11 & 12: SGD optimizer, max email length= 500, batch size= 64, 3 epochs

VII. CONCLUSION

The highest accuracy was achieved with the LSTM model, with an accuracy of 98.32% and a ROC-Score of 96.57%. This conforms with previous studies that have shown that RNNs are a reasonable method of classifying textual data. Nevertheless, CNN's highest accuracy of 96.52% and ROC-Score of 96.16% was pretty close. The histograms will show, for both CNN and LSTM, that the Adam Optimizer always performs better than the SGD optimizer. These results are not surprising since the Adam Optimizer makes use of the characteristics of the SGD and also includes features of another optimizer. For the activation function, however, there is not a clear answer. The ReLU activation function performed better with CNN, but on the average, the Sigmoid activation function performed with LSTM.

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